

FORMATION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, the formation of entrepreneurship skills and improvement of economic knowledge in elementary school students is described in detail.

Key words: entrepreneurial skills, methods of forming entrepreneurial skills, economic education, economic education, theoretical and practical considerations

"The dream of a new Uzbekistan, speaking in relation to our days, belongs to the present requirement, ideological and spiritual that determines its original appearance, driving forces and factors the basis, the creativity characteristic of our people and our large-scale reforms is a clear expression», Economy is production, distribution and trade, as well as goods and the field of study of consumption of services. In general, it is scarce resources practices related to the production, use and management of discourses and material expressions defined as a social sphere that emphasizes. Entrepreneurship means that people take risks for profit using funds, property, knowledge and capabilities to produce goods and provide services activity is understood. They create goods and services for profit people who take risks are understood. Economy has its place in the state It is the main network of complex infrastructure.

In this regard, the President if we look at the framework of the past years. 2018 "Active entrepreneurship innovative ideas and 21 trillion within the framework of

the state program named "technology support".

76,000 projects worth 1 billion soums and 1 billion dollars have been implemented in recent years shows the result of our work that started with "Every family is an entrepreneur", "Youth - About 2 trillion soums have been allocated within the framework of programs such as "our future". More than 600 business projects were implemented.

When we talk about the tasks ahead of us in the field of economy, first of all, it is comprehensive It should be noted that the economic reforms basically embody the following goals.

- Open economy, healthy competition, business and investment environment

A prerequisite for improvement is the improvement of conditions.

- reduction of state participation in the economy through rapid development of the private sector increase new jobs.

- able to realize strategic tasks related to economic development training of qualified personnel. Priority tasks to achieve these and similar goals implementation is required.

It is of particular importance to conduct research on improving theoretical and methodological aspects of primary education, formation of economic knowledge in primary school students, clarification of didactic-pedagogical possibilities and methods of educational situations aimed at formation of economic knowledge. This explains the need to create a methodical system aimed at organizing the educational process that forms economic knowledge in elementary school students. In the educational experience of developed countries, it is important to carry out scientific research on the development of students' abilities, the effective use of didactic, creative, integrative, economic and professional knowledge.

Economic knowledge.

It includes concrete and practical components of economic education, and at the same time, the activity of the teacher and the student is directed towards one goal

in the development of economic knowledge.

The main components of providing economic knowledge are the content of economic education (economic competence), economic literacy, economic knowledge, skills and qualifications, practical experience, competence.

Economic education is a mandatory part of education, the main purpose of which is to form a student's personality, to adapt to market conditions, and to prepare personnel who can carry out their activities economically.

Economic culture is a set of intellectual, emotional and practical components, moral and spiritual relations that allow a person to understand himself in economic activity and behavior in society, to integrate himself into social and economic conditions projected for his adaptation.

It is necessary to pay attention to the psychological-pedagogical features and influencing factors of this process in the formation of economic knowledge among elementary school students. The period of entering the general secondary school is characterized as the first opportunity given to the child to determine his position in the system of personal society relations, and in this process, they understand that family and society are of great importance in human life. A child who enters primary school experiences various emotions and experiences. In it, the place of impressionability, scattered and changing attention is replaced by the desire for knowledge, the need to express one's opinion clearly and broadly in connection with entering school.

Regarding work with elementary school students with different levels of knowledge, the famous scientist L.V. Zankov: "In order to move forward without "crawling" at the end of development, a perfect study of the individual characteristics of each child, his level of physical and mental development , it is necessary to perfectly know the level of thinking, speech, memory, knowledge and skills", expressed his opinion. The observations confirmed the scientifically based opinions of the scientist and showed that children have unique individual

characteristics not only physically, mentally, character, ability, interest, attitude to things and even imagination.

Entrepreneurship!

This phenomenon and concept seems very simple, obvious to everyone at first glance. In fact, it is a very complex, multifaceted and, moreover, a fundamental socio-economic phenomenon.

Y. Schumpeter, who is considered an entrepreneurship ideologist, emphasized that entrepreneurship is a phenomenon characteristic of all types of socio-economic systems, not only a component of them, but also a driving force of the economy. Entrepreneurship is proving to be such a force in the social and economic development of Uzbekistan and in mitigating the negative effects of the global financial and economic crisis and is becoming a leading sector. In 2008, 48.2 percent of the country's gross domestic product, 76 percent of the employed population, and 70 percent of the population's income fell to small business and private entrepreneurship. In 2010, its share in the gross domestic product was 50 - It is planned to reach 52 percent.

However, all aspects and functional properties of entrepreneurship have not yet been sufficiently studied, and as a result, its potential has not been fully mobilized. So, the science of the basics of entrepreneurship has huge tasks ahead of it. Such tasks can be summarized as follows:

- 1) in the field of theory: broader and deeper research of the entrepreneurial phenomenon, defining its fundamental functional properties and forming a comprehensive theoretical model;
- 2) in the field of methodology: enrichment and serious improvement of the methodology of theoretical-practical research currently formed and supported with new and existing effective methods and approaches;

Entrepreneurship starts with a business idea. How well the business idea is chosen business is one of the most basic and initial factors of success. But

business an idea alone is not enough for a successful business. For him, accurate accounts - to the books It is necessary to make a based plan. We have a minor in entrepreneurship in general secondary schools How can we do business? This is mainly from private business we can use. That is, we can do it in cooperation with our family members. Our great ancestor Amir Temur's "Businessman, determination of courage and courage." "One firm entrepreneur and alert person is better than thousands of idle and indifferent people." if we interpret the fertilizer. During the Middle Ages, it can be seen that a businessman, an entrepreneur, thousands and thousands of smart people have nothing to do without action is said to be the best of people. It is said that they are beneficial to people.

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